

**THE LANGUAGE OF ADVERTISING AND LINGUO-STYLISTIC
FEATURES OF ITS TEXT**

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ABSTRACT

Advertising language - simply a synthesis of extra linguistic and linguistic modes of communication governed by the principles of mass communication and general literary rules, as well as a specific language structure that allows for specific information to the addressee considering cultural, sociological factors and psycholinguistic characteristics of the language. This article, examines the peculiarities of the style of advertising texts, classifies advertising texts based on criteria such as the advertising object, target audience, media-advertising medium.

Keywords: sociolinguistics, advertising language, social, information, consumer, target audience, media-advertising.

INTRODUCTION

It is undeniable fact that currently, linguists pay great attention to advertising texts, advertising messages as one of the varieties of the "media text". Advertising is one of the most important factors of mass culture reflecting the life of modern society, it is a source of information about the national and cultural specifics of the native-speaking people and serves to exchange information in the process of social activity of people and their speech communication. Without any doubt, the topic is very relevant and reliable. Even if you don't read newspapers or watch TV, advertising appears to you as an obligatory element of the urban environment and fills all the media. In addition, advertising accompanies our life everywhere: on TV, on the radio, on the Internet, in newspapers and magazines, on the streets of the city.

So what does it carry with it? What is the language of advertising? What are its features? All these questions predetermined the purpose of the work – to study the advertising language and analyze the features of the advertising text.

To achieve the goal, the following tasks were set:

- to identify the role of advertising in the life of modern society;
- determine the main purpose of the advertising text;
- distinguish between the concepts of "advertising" and "advertisement";
- identify ways to classify advertising texts;
- to determine the significance and structure of the verbal component of advertising;
- to consider the linguistic and stylistic features of advertising texts.

ADVERTISING EFFECTIVENESS, PURPOSE, AND STRATEGIES

The advertising text means a complete graphic-textual unity. It follows from this definition of the advertising text that its components are both verbal and non-verbal means. Additionally, it influences the politics and structure of the media, turning them into a powerful lever of the economy. Moreover, advertising promotes ideas and values that are of key importance for the development of the economy. It actually regulates the consumer cycle, forcing people to buy things, use them and throw them away, then to purchase new ones. With the help of mass media advertising has a formative influence on the mass consciousness, promotes certain life values and attitudes. The main purpose of the advertising text is to convince the audience of the need to purchase a particular product or service. In terms of their importance in the global information process, advertising texts can only be compared with news texts. In English, two autonomous lexical units which are given below formed from one Latin word *advertere*, meaning turn around, are conveniently used to distinguish these two close, but different in meaning concepts:

1. advertising in the sense of «the industry that produces advertisements to be shown on television, printed in newspapers, magazines, etc.»; «the activity of advertising» (Oxford Advanced Learners` Dictionary); «the business of encouraging people to

buy goods by means of advertisements» (London Dictionary of English Language and Culture);

2. advertisement in the meaning of «a public notice offering or asking for goods, services, etc.» (OALD); «something used for advertising things, such as a notice on a wall or in a newspaper; or a short film shown on television» (LDELIC).

Any arbitrarily taken advertising text is perceived as advertising only in the unity of its verbal-graphic or audiovisual embodiment. Among the many ways of classifying advertising texts, three of the most traditional can be distinguished, based on the following criteria: the advertised object; the target audience; the media carrier of advertising. Thematic analysis of advertising shows that among the most common advertised products include cosmetics, perfumes, food and medicines, household appliances, clothing, cars. We can say that this conceptual set is universal for the advertising market of any country. At the same time, despite the general process of globalization of the advertising market, the thematic structure of advertising is culturally specific: the content of advertising in each individual country is characterized by a number of noticeable differences reflecting the peculiarities of social development in this particular cultural and linguistic area. The subject of advertising has a noticeable effect on the style of the advertising text. The language of fashion advertising is often based on tactile sensations, which is achieved through the use of adjectives that convey the quality of touch, the convenience of form and physical comfort. The advertising text tries to convey the properties of the advertised product both with the help of images and with the help of language, for example, the style of advertising expensive perfumes is usually refined and expressive:

„M“ is for moments you'll never forget.

For days marvelous with flowers and laughter.

For nights magical with means and old promises.

„M“ Fragrances by Henry C. Miner.

It's Magic.

Advertising cosmetics and perfumes for women in most cases is characterized by an exquisite style, replete with connotative phrases and other means of expression,

which gives the text a very special sound, a unique tonality: Inside this jar you'll find a radiantly-glowing skin, naturally-blushed cheeks, wondrous eyes and colour-kissed lips. Suddenly your skin has a radiant sun-kissed glow.

The style of car advertising seeks to recreate the impression of speed and efficiency: Its sleek, sporty styling shows a careful attention to aerodynamics. Low-slanting hood. Sharp high-tipped rear end. Air-clam front spoiler. And a wedge shape that slices air cleanly – all of which adds up to better fuel economy;

Classification by media-advertising medium – divides advertising into print (in newspapers and magazines), television, radio and Internet advertising. So, advertising on television is primarily a memorable video or a vivid visual image, accompanied by a minimal verbal text, often reduced to a brief advertising slogan. The main media feature of radio advertising is the use of all the richness of shades of the human voice and audio effects. Advertising in the press is based on a combination of a graphic or photo image with a verbal text of various lengths: from a short title to an expanded main text. The advantage of advertising in a newspaper is a large audience coverage at relatively low costs. Advertising placed in a special magazine aimed at a certain circle of readers accurately reaches the required audience. Radio advertising combines targeting the target audience with a fairly high frequency of playback. Finally, advertising on television is considered the most effective and expensive, as it provides huge opportunities in terms of influencing the audience.

The effectiveness of an advertising text depends on the successful combination of all its components: image, sound, image, verbal fabric. At the same time, researchers note the paramount importance of the verbal component of advertising – the verbal text. The verbal part of the advertising text has an internal structure: as a rule, this is the title, the main advertising text and the echo phrase. The purpose of the advertising title is to attract the attention of the audience and arouse interest in the advertised product or service. The advertising title contains an advertising appeal and the main advertising argument, which subsequently develops in the main advertising text, for example:

Carlsberg. Probably the best beer in the world.

EFG Private Bank: ... in tune with our clients.

An investment bank of global intelligence. Warburg Dillon Bank.

The purpose of the main advertising text is to tell in more detail about the advantages of the advertised product. The development of the main argument in the main advertising text is based on a number of different techniques: this may be an indication of the high quality of the subject of advertising, an appeal to the rational principle, an appeal to emotional sensory perception, the use of well-known images and socially significant stereotypes, emphasizing exceptionally favorable terms of sale, as well as a direct conviction of the need to purchase. The main advertising text varies in length from a relatively small (20-30 words) to a fairly detailed (80-100 words). The structure of the main advertising text reflects the communicative strategy chosen by its compilers, and can be based on the following communicative models: the inverted pyramid model; advertising comparison; plot or dramatized advertising; advertising-instruction; advertising-dialogue; advertising-question or riddle, paradox; advertising with the participation of famous personalities; advertising with the participation of ordinary consumers. The inverted pyramid model means that the first phrase of the text, in which the most important and weighty arguments are concentrated, carries the greatest information load. For example, in an advertisement for an English consulting firm «London Economics»: London Economics is Europe's Leading economics consultancy. We have over 80 consulting staff in London, Melbourne, Boston, Brussels, Dublin and Tokyo and operate worldwide. Our clients include major multinational companies, governments and international agencies.

Advertising-comparison is based on the comparison of the advertised product with similar, but presented by other firms and organizations. At the same time, the laws of the advertising market prohibit giving the name of a competitor company, so as not to harm its business reputation, for instance: All investment banks say they do the same things. One does them differently. Warburg Dillon Bank has a global mandate, yet our thinking is a world apart from standardized, rigid and restrictive.

Plot or dramatized advertising is most often used on television, since it is the capabilities of television that allow you to "dramatize" an advertising idea, embodying it in the form of a specific plot, as, for example, it is done in a series of commercials for English chocolate "Twiks". The main text of instructional advertising is a consistent description of consumer actions, made in the form of instructions, which successfully combines the necessary argumentation with a stable, easily recognizable form of text. The advertising-dialogue communicative model is successfully used both on radio and on television, providing the compilers of the advertising text with unlimited opportunities in the manifestation of originality and wit. The argumentation in the main text of the advertising question is constructed in the form of a series of questions- The world is shrinking. Whereas your scope is constantly growing. Theoretically. And Practically? After all what could be closer to your wishes than a bank with a perspective as broad as your own? Are you looking for partner near you? Simply call our automatic fax service in Germany.

The communicative strategy of advertising with the participation of famous people is based on the consumer's trust in the testimonies of the stars about the high quality of the goods, as well as on the desire to imitate one or another prestigious image. Do you want to be like the courageous Pierce Brosnan in the role of James Bond? Wear an expensive Swiss <<Omega>> watch. Advertising based on the testimonies of the average consumer is also highly effective and is often used as a communication strategy for building the main advertising text. The so-called echo phrase (in the English version of tagline) completes the verbal part of the advertising text, which also carries a large functional load. Firstly, the echo phrase repeats the main advertising argument in one form or another; secondly, it gives the advertising text completeness. In the final echo phrase, the name of the advertised trademark or product sounds in combination with a memorable expression or advertising slogan, for example: Swiss Line. The right direction. Star Alliance. The airline network for Earth. Mitsubishi Electric. Sometimes invisible, sometimes high profile, always at the front.

THE LINGUOSTYLISTIC FEATURES OF ADVERTISING TEXTS

With the aim of intense concentrated impact, advertising uses a rich range of expressiveness at all language levels. Metaphor, comparison, parallelism, various types of repetitions, alliteration, onomatopoeia, memorable phrases, rhythmically organized sentences, rhymed slogans and other expressive stylistic means, concentration of imperative verb forms and connotative adjectives - all this is widely represented in advertising texts. The language of advertising is extremely saturated with techniques of expressive stylistics. The creators of the advertising text masterfully use all the possibilities of word-making, finding advantages both in an exquisite expressive style and in a clear, simple presentation. The frequent use of imperative verb forms significantly enhances the dynamism of the advertising appeal, for example: See. Buy. Fly. Amsterdam Shopping Centre.

Verbal combinations of the type :Buy this, Discover that, Try some today, Don't forget, Treat yourself and others are very common in English-language advertising. The most commonly used verbs in the imperative include the following:

Here are some examples:

Buy the car. Own the road (Pontiac Grand Am).

Drive the new Paseo. Fall in love. Your future awaits down the road (Toyota Paseo).

Discover a new sense of daytime well – being for your skin. Bienfait Total (Lancome).

Since one of the most important components of the advertising text is the description of the advertised product or service, attributive phrases, which include adverbs and adjectives, carry a large functional load. They trigger the mechanisms of imagination, appealing to the senses and highlighting the most attractive sides and qualities in the advertised product, help to create that unique tone of advertising appeal that allows you to convey the qualities and merits of the advertised item: Seasons change, Spring gives way to Summer and the mood becomes lighter and more sensuous. So it is with the Rennie Mackintosh Collection – a beautifully crafted range of Gold or Sterling Silver Jewellery. Each piece has been designed to balance

timeless elegance with tasteful modernity. All intended to reflect every mood and created to uniquely compliment you (Rennie Mackintosh jewelry advertisement).

The most commonly used adjectives in English - language advertising include:

Adjectives indicating the authenticity of a trademark are often found :genuine, authentic and original. The adjective new is most often used it can be found in almost every second advertising text, for example: – New LASH OUT extra extending mascara with a new advanced protein formula.

But at the same time, advertising texts should not use words and phrases that can mislead the consumer about the real qualities and properties of the proposed product. Therefore, adjectives with excellent evaluative connotations such as magic and miraculous are increasingly rare in English advertising texts. Restrictive measures have also been taken regarding some aspects of the use of female images in advertising. With all the abundance of linguistic means of influence, which is characteristic of advertising texts, it must be remembered that the saturation of the verbal part of advertising with various means of expression does not guarantee success at all. A distinctive feature of successful advertising is the harmonious combination of the main advertising idea with those means of expression that most correspond to this idea. This is expressed, in particular, in finding the only true tone for the problem of studying and preserving the languages and cultures of the peoples of the world through advertising, which gives the text a special energy, enhancing its cumulative figurative and linguistic impact on the mass audience. Here are some examples of the most successful verbal embodiment of an advertising intention:

- Maybe she's born with it. Maybe it's Maybelline (Alliteration).
- Don't be vague. Ask for Haig (Rhyme).
- Our jeans fit your genes (Homonyms).
- Natural Beauty. Natural Ingredients. Natural Glow (Repetition).
- No other hair spray feels so fine. No other hair spray brushes out so easily. No other hair spray leaves your hair so shiny and yet soft to touch. No wonder its preferred by the world's finest salons. L'Oreal (Anaphora).

CONCLUSION

All in all, the structure of the advertising text differs from other texts in terms of the level and scope of use of linguistic units. It is advisable to form the advertising text based on the nature of the language. Exact translation of advertising texts in another language does not always give the desired effect. Therefore, it is necessary to form an advertising text in our language by choosing units that differ in their lexical and semantic features.

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